

UNIVERSITY OF
BIRMINGHAM

Research Software Group

Advanced Research Computing

Annual Report 2024

Advanced Research Computing	3
Research Software Group	5
RSE Service	7
Research Data Science Service	11
BEAR Apps	12
Case Studies	15
Training	32
Conferences and Events	34
Contact Us	39

Advanced Research Computing

Advanced Research Computing (ARC) designs, operates and supports a range of services for researchers at the University of Birmingham and beyond.

Birmingham researchers benefit from ARC's award-winning Birmingham Environment for Academic Research (BEAR). These BEAR services are designed to support research and many are free at the point of use. More than 4600 research projects with over 5200 staff and students are currently registered to use BEAR services. Since starting to collect the data in 2021, our academics have told us about over 1400 publications that resulted in full or in part from using BEAR.

Baskerville is a national accelerated compute system funded by EPSRC and UKRI, and (like BEAR) routinely receives excellent feedback from researchers who use it. In 2024 Baskerville was used by many researchers from the University of Birmingham, the Baskerville consortium (the Rosalind Franklin Institute, the Alan Turing Institute, and Diamond Light Source), and the wider UK research community via EPSRC's Access to HPC calls. At the time of writing, we have been informed about 75 publications acknowledging Baskerville.

ARC is based in IT Services, led by Carol Sandys and reports to the Chief Information Officer, Mark Gee. The Team has grown substantially over recent years, and now has over 40 posts. The University's commitment to BEAR was reasserted in the most

recent Vice Chancellor's Review of IT Services and in the Digital Strategy, and our services continue to expand to meet the needs of the research community.

ARC is comprised of three groups:

- Architecture, Infrastructure and Systems Group
- Researcher Engagement and Data Group
- Research Software Group

These groups provide experts to design and operate ARC's advanced compute, storage and related services and also specialists at engaging with and supporting our wide and varied community of researchers.

The report that follows introduces the work of the Research Software Group and gives brief case studies to illustrate the benefits that partnership with the RSG, and ARC, can deliver.

- Carol Sandys, Head of Advanced Research Computing and Researcher Engagement

Research Software Group

The Research Software Group (RSG) is part of Advanced Research Computing at the University of Birmingham.

The RSG has grown substantially since it was formed in 2017. At the end of 2024 the team has 28 posts, split into four job types:

- Research Applications Specialists - who support users of BEAR's high performance computing services BlueBEAR, BEAR Cloud and Baskerville. A significant part of this work is installing, curating and supporting over a thousand applications and libraries available on these systems.
- Research Software Engineers - who join research projects or groups for longer-term funded collaborations. They also provide free advice, coaching and coding work for any University researcher, from PhD students to senior academics.
- Research Data Scientists - who collectively run our Research Data Science Service, launched in 2023. They work on projects funded by grants and also pump priming projects funded by the Institute for Data and AI.
- Dev Ops Engineers - who develop and maintain our internal information systems and tooling.

BEAR Software's mission is summed up in the words of the Software Sustainability Institute: "better software, better research".

The Research Software Group exists to:

- Enable the University of Birmingham's research community to get the best from their research software
- Provide specialist software engineering and data science advice and support to researchers
- Help to enhance the University's reputation for high quality research
- Help researchers get the most from BEAR services, maximising the return on the University's investment in BEAR

RSE Service

The term 'Research Software Engineer' (RSE) was coined in March 2012 at the Collaborations Workshop and you can find all about the history of RSEs from the State of the Nation report from 2017¹ and 'A not-so-brief history of Research Software Engineers'².

RSEs use software engineering practices to develop and support software in research applications. They focus on reproducibility, reusability, and accuracy of data analysis and applications created for research. RSEs are frequently multi-skilled and adaptable, turning their hands to anything from coaching researchers in software engineering, optimising high-throughput data pipelines, developing full-stack web applications, or implementing AI models on supercomputers - anything really that helps researchers do better research. All of the RSEs at ARC have a wide variety of technical skills and most have been researchers at some point in their careers.

The Value of Good Research Software Engineering

Research software engineering covers a broad spectrum of applications and good research software engineering principles result in more reproducible and accurate research.

Our RSE engagements are always collaborative, with the RSE and researchers working together. The need for this is highlighted by the following quote from the Government Office for Science:

¹ Brett, A. et al. (2017). Research Software Engineers: State of the Nation Report 2017. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.495360>

² Hettrick, S. (2016). A not-so-brief history of Research Software Engineers. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10076740>

'Domain scientists need to have the relevant skills to be able to map scientific problems to computational solutions. It is also important that they work closely with RSEs and other computing professionals to produce efficient and reliable software.'³

Having an RSE (or two) on your research project is a cost effective way of increasing the quality of your research and gaining a valuable collaborator!

RSE Service: Advice, Coaching, Coding and Mentoring

The Research Software Engineering Service (RSE Service) consists of a range of offerings to all researchers in the University. These services include advice, coaching, coding and mentoring sessions and engagements.

RSE Services are offered on a paid-for and a free basis. The paid-for services are usually funded through researchers' grants and allow for longer coaching or coding engagements, from one month to several years. Typical arrangements for funded engagements involve paying for a percentage of one or more RSEs to work on a defined project. The free services include one-off advice sessions, mentoring and short coaching or coding engagements.

More detail on our funded and free services can be found on the [RSE Service](#) section of our website.

³ Government Office for Science. (2021). Large-scale computing: the case for greater UK coordination, p.63. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/654a4025e2e16a000d42aaef/UK_Computing_report_-_Final_20.09.21.pdf

RSE Service: Funded Engagements

The RSG has 15 RSEs available for funded projects with a wide variety of skills and domain knowledge. RSEs can be included in grant applications or bought out using existing research funding.

The idea is to allow a research group/project to pay for one or more RSEs with particular skills for a period of time. This could be a short project like two RSEs running a two-week workshop, or a long project like 50% FTE for 2 years. To achieve this we have a central pool of RSEs that work on funded projects for the majority of their role.

We offer two main types of funded engagement:

- Long projects (typically 3 months or more) should be defined as essentially 50% of an RSE, or multiples, e.g. two RSEs at 50% for 2 years. For each 50% FTE we will actually quote 45% of the RSE, and 5% of a senior member of the RSG who will provide code review, support, mentoring and advice to the RSE. Our policy is that no RSE will work more than 45% on a single long project, so for larger requirements we will provide multiple RSEs as needed.
- Short projects (a month or less) can have any percentage FTE of RSEs - e.g. 20% of one RSE and 90% of another for a month, depending on availability.

It is rare that an RSE engagement will have static requirements specified up front and much more likely that the researcher and RSE will work together defining and re-defining the goals of the project as time goes on. As such we encourage you to think of RSE engagements as research collaborations, and RSEs as more like researchers than software consultants.

If you are considering including an RSE on a grant application please get in touch with us at an early stage by emailing bear-rsg@contacts.bham.ac.uk. For more detail about our funded engagements and for instructions on how to include RSEs in a [Work-tribe](#) project, please see the [funded engagements page](#) on our website.

RSE Service: Free Engagements

The RSE Service offers advice and mentoring, and short coaching or coding engagements free to all researchers in the University. There is limited availability for our free services and there may be a delay before we can schedule new engagements.

Advice: We are happy to offer advice on any aspect of research software that leads to improved reliability and maintainability of research.

Mentoring: We offer a mentoring option for those who would like to develop a longer-term relationship with the RSG. These often take the form of an informal conversation a few times a year.

Coaching: An RSE can be requested for multiple half-day coaching sessions (max. 10). During these sessions the RSE would meet the researcher or research group (physically or virtually) to work with them to complete specific agreed objectives.

Coding: We offer up to ten days of coding time, typically delivered over several weeks. Examples might include translating an algorithm into a different programming language or adding parallelisation or GPU support to an application.

For all these engagements, we write some lightweight paperwork to agree who will do what, and when. To request advice, mentoring, coaching or coding please email bear-rsg@contacts.bham.ac.uk and specify which service you would like along with some details of the work.

Research Data Science Service

The Research Data Science Service is delivered by the Research Software Group on behalf of the Institute for Data and AI (IDAI). We aim to improve and enable state-of-the-art data science research at the University through a range of complementary services. We are funded by both IDAI and the Centre for Artificial Intelligence in Government (CAIG).

Goals

The Research Data Science Service exists to:

- Facilitate data-intensive research at the University of Birmingham by providing specialist data science support and advice.
- Help researchers to increase the competitiveness of funding applications involving a data science or AI component.
- Support open science and reproducibility by helping University of Birmingham researchers to share their data and code effectively and with impact.

Activities

- Institute-funded work - including pre-award advice and support, post-award advice and help with publications, data science training, and working on Institute-funded pump-priming projects.
- Grant-funded work - funding a Research Data Scientist's time to collaborate on research projects.

Further information can be found on the Research Data Science Service section of our website.

solve issues with installations. By doing this, we can ensure that the important libraries, such as those for mathematical operations and network communication, work efficiently and effectively.

The RASs also maintain a suite of **ReFrame** tests, which enable ARC both to check the continuing performance of the HPC and to aid in debugging issues when there is a fault. By running thousands of short test jobs daily we can be confident in the quality of the application stack provided to our research community.

What a RAS Does

- Application and Software Support:
 - Installs software applications on the University's high performance computing (HPC) systems.
 - Compiles and optimises software packages for the HPC environment, using the **EasyBuild** framework.
- User Support:
 - Provides comprehensive technical support to the University's researchers, helping them use our systems well.
 - Provides application-specific support and assists users in debugging problems.
- User Training:
 - Assists the team in providing regular training to staff and research students from a variety of disciplines across the university.

- User Documentation:
 - Maintains and extends our public-facing documentation sites. These sites primarily comprise technical documentation and apply to all services provided to researchers. The documentation can be viewed at:
 - ★ <https://docs.bear.bham.ac.uk>
 - ★ <https://docs.baskerville.ac.uk>
- Internal Documentation:
 - Maintains and extends our internal wiki pages, ensuring that knowledge is shared across the team.
- Collaboration and Communication:
 - Works closely with colleagues from other groups within Advanced Research Computing as well as with staff from across IT Services.
 - Collaborates with researchers from across all areas of the University.

Case Studies

Advice Sessions

Advice sessions are usually provided by two members of the group, sometimes pulling in those with specific and relevant skills, and frequently form the first in-person contact between researchers and the RSG. They can, however, also form a more tightly-focused part of a longer project.

The sessions cover a wide range of topic areas, and sessions from the past year have included requirements gathering for a future project the team will work on, discussion of appropriate software and techniques when approaching a potential or existing project, how to handle web accessibility requirements, suitable wording and assistance with providing accurate financial quotes for writing grant proposals including future work or resource provision from the RSG, working together on scripts or providing code review feedback, advising how researchers can prepare specialist data such as patient data for analysis, anonymisation of data, relevant methodologies when using BlueBEAR and HPC, utilising AI / ML, or putting researchers in contact with groups with similar aims or experience.

Example Advice Sessions

A postdoctoral researcher in the School of Physics and Astronomy requested advice regarding how to establish the best machine learning algorithm and assistance figuring out appropriate parameters for the analysis. Two RSEs with HPC experience met with the researcher and discussed the size and complexity of the dataset, past challenges encountered in approaching the issue and made suggestions as to a possible alternative algorithm and some additional techniques for validation and avoiding bias.

Another advice session involved a request for support from a professor in the School of Economics around effectively costing a grant proposal they were drafting, which would involve a web project and appropriate VM hosting. An RSE with experience working

on web projects and a RAS met with him and discussed the project and a comparable example site he had brought to us. In light of this, they made recommendations around appropriate web technologies and broke the requirements down into two distinct tasks identified (web front end design and visualisation including Natural Language type search functionality employed to enable filtering of the dataset / optimisation of data management and processing), and provided approximate costs for storage, a virtual machine for 5 years with capacity for a database, and RSE time. Additional suggestions were made around the most efficient system to use to process the data, with BlueBEAR being the preferred option.

Coaching Case Study - Optimising or Accelerating a JAX-Based Pipeline

Researchers

- Dr Rachel Howe
- Dr Martin Nielsen

Technologies

Python, JAX, NumPyro, MCMC, Bayesian inference, BlueBEAR, HPC, GPU

Project Description

We were approached by Dr Rachel Howe and Dr Martin Nielsen who are working on analysing large datasets to fit oscillation modes in the solar frequency-power spectrum. Their current CPU-based approach is computationally intensive, limiting its scalability for larger simulations. To address this challenge, they sought assistance from the Research Software Group to accelerate their code.

By profiling their code, we identified performance bottlenecks and suggested optimisations and improvements, such as exploring alternative libraries like NumPyro. This library has been shown to efficiently utilise GPU resources and therefore accelerate the demanding part of the pipeline. By providing guidance on efficient GPU utilisation, we empowered the researchers to optimise their code and achieve significant performance gains. Additionally, we suggested implementing checkpointing to allow for job resumption in case of interruptions, improving resource utilisation on the HPC system.

Beyond technical optimisations, we emphasised the importance of software engineering principles. By adopting a structured approach to development, including practices like clear documentation, modular code design and separation of concerns, the

researchers were able to write more maintainable, efficient and reliable code. This collaborative effort has not only accelerated scientific discovery but has also empowered the researchers to become more proficient software engineers.

Researcher Feedback

At a very basic level, while we already had the fundamental parts of the code written, I found it very useful to get a code review from an independent source. Just to make sure we were not missing completely obvious things in terms of code efficiency and implementation on the BlueBEAR HPC. I was also very happy to find, with the help of the RSEs, that our particular problem can be deployed on a GPU architecture, and that it provides a significant gain in computational efficiency. To my knowledge this is the first time this has been shown in our field.

- **Dr Martin Nielsen**

I've learned a lot in the course of the engagement, and I'm happy that our code is now running around two orders of magnitude faster than when we started. There is still work to be done, but we have strategies for going forward.

- **Dr Rachel Howe**

Coding Case Study - HadGEM2 Build for BlueBEAR

Researcher

Dr Peter Hopcroft

Technologies

Fortran, Bash, SVN

Project Description

HadGEM2 is a climate prediction model developed by the Met Office. Before this project this software was only available on the HPC systems arc3 and arc4 at the University of Leeds. The objective of this project

was to determine the necessary dependencies for HadGEM2, and modify the bash scripts provided by the team at Leeds to build HadGEM2, prepare a model and run that model on BlueBEAR. The project was successful in achieving its goal, enabling new research to be conducted by the Geography department at the University.

Researcher Feedback

The installation of the Earth System model HadGEM2 on BlueBEAR is a step change in climate research capability here in Birmingham. It allows us to directly simulate the coupling of the climate system to atmospheric constituents like desert dust and the greenhouse gas methane and to evaluate how these react on long-time scales in the past and potentially the future. Having this model working here has opened up several lines of enquiry that I've wanted to look at for a while and new simulations performed on BlueBEAR have helped to finalise results for two papers and are also contributing to two proposals.

- **Dr Peter Hopcroft**

Coding Case Study - CNearest Open Source Library - Regularized Stokeslet Fluid Modelling

Researchers

Professor David Smith

Technologies

C++

Project Description

Professor David Smith's research group have been working on computational methods for microscopic flow problems, with the particular aim of studying swimming cells such as spermatozoa, cilia-driven flows in reproduction and development, and the dynamics of large biomolecular constructs.

Their ambition is to develop methods that are efficient, accurate and easy for non-specialists to use. The research team have previously developed a numerical method (nearest-neighbour regularised stokeslets), which was implemented in MATLAB as NEAREST. The RSG were tasked with reimplementing this in C++ (for computational efficiency) in an accessible manner, thus furthering this ambition.

Simplified representations of the macromolecular structure of interest, with (a) force discretisation ($N = 384$) and (b) quadrature discretisation ($Q = 1689$) shown. Image publicly available [here](#)

Using the NEAREST codebase and the research team's original research papers⁴ as a guide, we were able to produce an open-source C++ library - currently under review at the Journal of Open Source Software (JOSS).

Researcher Feedback

We worked with the RSG who developed an extensible C++ codebase cNEAREST, with documentation and testing. The RSG team discovered an ambiguity in the original algorithm - which they solved - and proposed two further refinements: one modification of the algorithm to assist with interpretation and convergence testing, and a further modification to improve memory usage, greatly expanding the complexity of what can be solved. The implementation fits well with our ethos of having a low barrier to entry, minimising dependencies and providing a framework that can be built on in future work. The team also supported submission of the software to JOSS.

Working with the RSG team was a very positive experience. Along with clear communication throughout and excellent knowledge and professionalism in delivering the software and transferring their expertise, the team's depth of insight into improving the algorithm has materially advanced our research capabilities.

- **Professor David Smith**

⁴ Smith, D.J. (2018). A nearest-neighbour discretisation of the regularized stokeslet boundary integral equation. Journal of Computational Physics 358, pp.88-102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcp.2017.12.008>; and Gallagher, M.T. and Smith, D.J. (2018). Meshfree and efficient modeling of swimming cells. Phys. Rev. Fluids 3(5). <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevFluids.3.053101>

Coding Case Study - AI-Enabled Analysis of H&E Images from Sjögren Disease Patients

Researchers

- Dr Saba Nayar
- Dr Sebastian Gilbert
- Professor Fabian Spill

Technologies

Python, deep learning, computer vision, machine learning/AI, PyTorch, SLURM, Apptainer, GPUs/HPC

Project Description

Analysis of microscopy images from patient biopsies, particularly Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) staining, is pivotal in diagnosing various diseases, including cancers, infectious diseases, and inflammatory conditions. This Institute for Data and AI funded pump-priming project developed pilot analysis workflows to automatically analyse H&E images from patients with Sjögren Disease (SjD), a chronic autoimmune disease.

The images are very large, so we trained a deep neural network (UNET with custom PyTorch implementation) to identify the key regions of the tissue associate with the disease – specifically, lymphomononuclear cell clusters organized as periductal infiltrates

(foci), both with and without germinal centres. We then used a second pre-trained deep neural network (Hover-Net implemented in TIA-Toolbox framework) to identify the location and cell type of individual cells within these key regions. All model training and prediction was performed on GPUs within a containerised environment run on BlueBEAR. Going forward this framework will allow the researchers to automate the analysis of H&E images and study the spatial organisation of cells within these foci and their structural variations, advancing our understanding of SjD pathology. The ability to automate H&E image analysis holds significant promise: it paves the way for optimized, tissue-based pathological scoring in clinical trials and may lead to more efficient, consistent histopathological assessments. This approach could support new diagnostic tools and deepen insights into the disease mechanisms underlying SjD.

Researcher Feedback

Jeremy Pike and Kamilla Kopec-Harding's work as a Research Data Scientists on this project was instrumental in developing a robust, reproducible pipeline for the automated analysis of H&E-stained biopsy images, leveraging deep learning to identify key tissue regions and cell types in Sjögren Disease. Their contributions to the code's scalability, reusability, and documentation ensured accessibility for researchers across various technical backgrounds, enabling more efficient and insightful analysis of large-scale medical imaging data. The support from the Institute for Data and AI team was critical in forming new links between researchers in the College of Engineering, Physical and Mathematical Sciences (EPS) and the Medical School. The Medical School benefited from new algorithms to analyse data and gain insights into medical problems, while EPS researchers obtained access to new data to test the real-world applicability of their algorithms. This collaborative effort exemplifies how interdisciplinary partnerships can drive innovation and lead to significant advancements in medical research.

- **Dr Saba Nayar**

Coding Case Study - Monitoring Motor Recovery

Researchers

- Professor Dario Farina
- Dr Jumpei Kashiwakura
- Dr Patrick Sagastegui
- Dr Vishal Rawji

Technologies

MongoDB, Quarkus, Docker

Project Description

This was a collaboration brought about through the Centre for Systems Modelling and Quantitative Biomedicine (SMQB)'s seedcorn programme, run by Dr Rebecca Ward: bringing together RSEs, the SMQB and researchers from Imperial College London. Jumpei and Patrick's research involves the creation of a medical device for monitoring and improving the motor recovery of patients (e.g. stroke victims). The RSG contribution was to write backend containerised systems to provide REST interfaces for the storage and retrieval of device and patient data from mobile devices. The RSEs involved with the project really enjoyed the challenge of this work, which used novel

microservices technologies and access to the prototype device throughout the engagement. The application that we developed had to adapt to constantly evolving and complex data requirements and needed to be performant to scale from research to production.

Dr Anja Borowicz-Richardson joined the collaboration as an Artist in Residence and provided some wonderful soundscapes that were inspired by this project.

Researcher Feedback

The Research Software Engineering Service team at the University of Birmingham, led by Dr Adrian Garcia, significantly accelerated the project and achieved remarkable progress in back-end hosting server development. We are very pleased with the outcome delivered by the team; communication, understanding of our goals, and synergy throughout the project.

- **Dr Jumpei Kashiwakura**

Coding Case Study - DIATOMIC: A Digital Twin for Birmingham

Researchers

- Dr Grant Wilson
- Dr Zoya Pourmirza

Technologies

Python, Django, MapBox, Prefect, PostGIS

Project Description

The RSG is currently working on three projects with Grant Wilson (School of Chemical Engineering) and Zoya Pourmirza (School of Computer Science) that share a common goal: to develop a digital twin of Birmingham.

The digital twin collates data from several online sources and presents them in an easy to access webpage format. The digital twin is a collaboration

between the University of Birmingham, Aston University, Birmingham City University, Birmingham City Council, Siemens Advanta, and the Connected Places Catapult.

The University of Birmingham's contribution to the digital twin gives us insights into the energy performance of buildings and the demand of electricity generation in the region. Users can interact with the platform with a map-based interface, allowing them to access the data they want in the particular area they are interested in.

The infrastructure for the digital twin is designed by Siemens Advanta and is based on the Azure Kubernetes Service of Microsoft Azure. The RSEs involved in the project are writing containerised components to be deployed on the Siemens infrastructure.

DIATOMIC is an exciting and innovative initiative with broad applications across sectors. It has strong potential for growth, positioning us to drive future innovations and impactful real-world research.

Coding Case Study - Swarm-VIP-Dynamic Data Acquisition and Database Building

Researchers

Dr Alan Wood

Technologies

MATLAB, FTP, GitLab

Project Description

The research team, lead by Dr Alan Wood, were building a 14-year time series dataset that consolidates a number of data sources to learn about the Earth's magnetic field and ionosphere. They had already developed a series of MATLAB scripts for consolidating the data, which required manually downloading thousands of data files. The team wanted to extend their code to automate downloading and synchronising the data from the European Space Agency's (ESA) Swarm mission. This project would enable future team members to further develop, build, and work with the dataset. Consequently, they approached the RSG for help, which led to a coding engagement that lasted seven weeks.

Initially, the RSEs met with Alan to discuss the project plan and review his existing codebase. They quickly identified the need to develop a custom MATLAB toolbox to provide a suite of functions which automate building their database. Additionally, Alan provided a detailed project specification and emphasised the need for complete documentation and example scripts. The RSEs identified an opportunity to utilise new MATLAB features which support sustainable software practice, such as unit testing and function input validation.

By the end of the engagement, the RSEs had created a MATLAB codebase, which they called Swarm Dynamic Toolbox. It provided a simple set of functions that may be used to fetch data from multiple sources, synchronise and align the data, then store it in a convenient form for future access. They documented the toolbox in an editable GitLab Wiki to allow Alan's team to use and build upon the codebase. The research team has since used this toolbox extensively in their work. Following the project, Alan reached out to the RSG to request help extending the toolbox. This led to a second successful engagement with the team in which RSEs enabled authenticated login to the ESA servers and support for additional data sources.

Researcher Feedback

The ARC team, particularly Alexander Lyttle, provided exactly what we needed, on time and in a thoroughly professional manner. Alexander and the wider team listened to what we needed and then developed the required toolbox. Crucially, these tools were documented in a manner which makes them accessible to other researchers. The toolbox has enabled us to deliver scientific results within the Swarm-VIP-Dynamic project. The Swarm-VIP-Dynamic team recently had a milestone meeting with the European Space Agency (ESA), who fund this project (ESA Contract No. 4000143413/23/I-EB). Not just was the milestone achieved (and the resulting payment from ESA to UoB is being processed), but we were invited to participate in two Contract Change Notices, which will provide funding of up to 200,000 EUR to the team for additional, collaborative projects.

In summary, the ARC team listened to our needs and delivered exactly what was required. They were a pleasure to work with and their actions are underpinning further income generation.

- **Dr Alan Wood**

Coding Case Study - Nano-org: A Database and Analysis Platform for Advanced Light Microscopy Data

Researchers

- Professor Dylan Owen
- Dr Sandeep Shirgill

Technologies

Web, Django, VMs, Python, HTML, CSS, JavaScript, Celery, SLURM, GPUs/HPC

Project Description

The [nano-org website](#) hosts a database for a form of advanced light microscopy data that provides the locations of individual proteins within cells as a list of coordinates with ultra-high precision (typically less than 40nm). Researchers from the global researcher community can upload/share their data and quantitatively compare it to other datasets. This comparison is enabled by automatic submission of analysis jobs to BlueBEAR that compare each new dataset to all datasets within the database⁵. The rendered image shows the distribution of actin within

⁵ Shirgill, S. et al. (2024). Nano-org, a functional resource for single-molecule localisation microscopy data. bioRxiv 2024-08. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.08.06.606779>

a cell - a cytoskeleton protein that forms filaments, which help to give the cell structure, shape and the ability to move⁶. It also shows how nano-org automatically divides the cell (blue polygon) into 3x3 micron regions (red squares) for downstream analysis.

We are currently developing new functionality that will allow researchers to identify and analyse how proteins cluster on the surface of cells. The distribution of proteins is first compared to random simulations to determine if there is organisation and unsupervised machine learning algorithms are subsequently used to group proteins into specific clusters. This cell surface organisation is a crucial part of how cells react to external factors, such as changes in hormone levels or a drug treatment, and is fundamentally linked to diseases including autoimmune disorders and cancer.

Researcher Feedback

Working alongside the Research Software Group has been a highly positive experience. Their expertise transformed a research concept into efficient, user-friendly software with enhanced functionality, making the research process smoother and more productive. They have been incredibly helpful throughout, always ready to provide guidance and support whenever needed.

- **Dr Sandeep Shirgill**

⁶ The raw data used to generate the image is from:
Jimenez, A., Friedl, K. and Letierrier, C. (2020). About samples, giving examples: Optimized Single Molecule Localization Microscopy. *Methods* 174, pp.100-114.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jymeth.2019.05.008>

Training

To support ARC's mission of supporting researchers in developing and using research software on their own systems as well as various tiers of HPC, we deliver a variety of training courses throughout the year. These are organised by ARC's Researcher Engagement and Data Group and delivered by a mixture of ARC staff and volunteers from across the University.

Our long-running Introduction to Linux and Introduction to BlueBEAR courses give researchers the fundamental knowledge necessary to run their analyses on HPC facilities like BlueBEAR. We taught these courses five times each and additionally taught the Introduction to BlueBEAR to the [Materials Simulation and Modelling Discussion Group](#), a BEAR Special Interest Group. This year also saw the first delivery of our Advanced BlueBEAR course, which is now a regular part of our training programme.

Very helpful when I asked questions about anything; took time to explain different things.

- **Attendee at Introduction to BlueBEAR**

The University is proud to be a Silver Member of [The Carpentries](#), a world-renowned programme of courses that teach foundational programming skills to researchers. We regularly teach Carpentries courses on Git, Python, R and MATLAB and are developing additional courses to deliver in 2025. Two ARC team members qualified as Carpentries instructors in 2024 and two more have begun the process. They add to the 10 instructors already in the RSG.

Very clear instruction and easy to follow on my personal machine, gave a good groundwork to explore other modules I need in my own time.

- **Attendee at Python Carpentries in October 2024**

Following feedback in the 2022 IT Needs of Active Research Survey, we have now developed a local version of the Carpentries course on Image Processing with Python. This course was delivered twice in 2024 and is now a regular item in our schedule.

Besides the Carpentries courses, we also regularly teach courses from NVIDIA's Deep Learning Institute, delivered by the RSG's NVIDIA University Ambassadors. At the University of Birmingham, we twice delivered the Fundamentals of Deep Learning course and will be expanding our provision, with two new NVIDIA Ambassadors in the team.

Finally, we also delivered bespoke training for our partners in the Baskerville consortium, in person at the Turing Institute in February and online over four weeks in June.

Overall, in 2024 we taught over 350 researchers across 30 courses, demonstrating the growing popularity of our training programme. We look forward to engaging with researchers in even more training in 2025!

Conferences and Events

BEAR Challenge

Our annual BEAR Challenge returned again from 24 to 26 June, with ten teams of students competing against each other to win prizes while learning lots about High Performance Computing and AI. The participants were all students from various taught programmes at the University. All the participants were granted access to Baskerville, our national Tier 2 High Performance Computing (HPC) system with 208 NVIDIA A100 GPUs. This year, we welcomed teams with students from Computer Science, Physics, Philosophy, Psychology, Mathematics and Cancer and Genomic Sciences.

There were 5 challenges over the three days, with the first day being spent learning how to login and use the Baskerville HPC system. On the second day, we welcomed Paul Graham from NVIDIA, who presented a challenge on training a neural network to classify tropical cyclones. Day 3 included the final challenge provided by Lenovo, to design a HPC cluster to meet a customer's needs. The students also benefited from careers talks from Lenovo, NVIDIA and ARC throughout the event.

The students' responses were very positive, for example:

It was an amazing event and through the experience I felt cared for and was truly interested in the challenges while gaining some fantastic insight from some incredible people.

We supported teams from BEAR Challenge to represent Birmingham at the national CIUK Cluster Challenge in December, so that they can continue their journey into exploring HPC in the short term, and hopefully as a career in the future.

See our [blog post](#) for a full description of the event, and lots more photos. See also [this blog post](#) for a student team member's reflections on this year's BEAR Challenge.

9th EasyBuild User Meeting

Two members of the BEAR Apps team (James & Simon) travelled to Umeå, Sweden, in April 2024 to attend the [9th EasyBuild User Meeting](#). The annual EasyBuild User Meetings are a staple of the BEAR Apps Team's calendar, where the RSG have had a regular presence since 2017, with Simon Branford now also being on the organising committee.

Simon presented twice at the event:

- [EasyBuild 5.0 \(including hands-on\)](#) covered information on the future direction and plans of the EasyBuild framework.
- [Baskerville @ University of Birmingham](#) described how the use of EasyBuild enabled rapid deployment of Baskerville.

It was a great opportunity to interact with other members of the international EasyBuild community, particularly given the importance of the framework in the day-to-day maintenance of our HPC software stacks.

HPC-SIG

The University of Birmingham has been a long-standing member and supporter of the HPC-SIG: The High Performance Computing Special Interest Group for UK Academia.

Ed is the Chair of the HPC-SIG, and Leo has recently been appointed its Communications Officer. Ed routinely chairs the meetings, and runs sessions such as the now traditional 'Fishbowl' panel, where volunteers must join the panel in order to join in the discussion (no questions or comments are allowed from the floor). This idea was borrowed from a similar panel at ISC.

Other members of the RSG (and the wider ARC) continue to support the HPC-SIG and regularly attend meetings. James Allsopp spoke at the Sheffield meeting in June on the topic of 'FlowCron – Using Globus to enable Function-as-a-service on HPC'.

RSE Midlands

The third RSE Midlands conference, RSE Midlands 2024, was hosted by the University of Warwick.

Several of the team attended again, with Gavin delivering a talk about the RSE Midlands Coding Club, reviewing the past talks and inviting others to contribute. James Tyrrell also spoke, sharing his experience of helping to run the centralised RSE service, involving line management, project management and service management.

We are excited to announce that RSE Midlands 2025 will be hosted in April at the University of Birmingham!

RSECon24

In September, RSECon24 was held in Newcastle. The international Research Software Engineering community convened for an exciting week of sessions, speakers, and networking. It brought together a mix of hundreds of software engineers, developers, researchers, community managers, funders and educators on a shared journey of learning and growth.

As part of RSECon24, James Tyrrell and Gavin Yearwood organised a RSE Regional Groups SIG Meeting: 'Regional RSE Groups are beginning to form across the UK with the aim of creating a skills network, a local hub for advice, and a great way to network and form collaborations. The Society of RSE formed a Special Interest Group (SIG) in 2021 to support the forming of regional groups. We are meeting in this lunchtime session during RSECon24 to get together and learn more about our community in relation to groups and regional groups.'

Several of the team attended RSECon24, as usual, attending a wide variety of sessions and events. We are looking forward to next year's RSECon25 which will be held in the University of Warwick, which is really close to Birmingham and so should allow lots of the team to attend.

The Second UK AI Conference 2024

In November the second UK AI conference 2024 was held in Birmingham. The conference allows researchers nationwide to share work on all aspects of AI, from theory and development to application and real-world implementation. The conference was attended by Alex, Vlad, and Simon from the RSG, who networked and heard about state-of-the-art AI research from various UK universities. Simon Hartley also presented a poster entitled: 'Supporting Non-traditional High Performance Compute Users to Benchmark and Run Deep Learning and Large Language Models on Tier 2 Systems', which was well received and generated queries about the Baskerville and Sulis Tier 2 systems. The poster represented the work of the group in teaching AI and promoting best practices for AI in Government and Social Science research.

RSG Hackathon

In April the RSG organised its first ever team hackathon. For two weeks, all team members had time set aside from their regular project work to join in the various sessions offered. We were encouraged to sign up for anything that was interesting to us or that we wanted to know more about, as well as to sessions where we had some knowledge or experience to share. As a growing team, it was a great opportunity for us to work with members of the team we don't regularly collaborate with, to learn from each other and to work on challenges together. All of the hackathon sessions were organised and led by team members and covered a wide range of topics and activities. Some of the sessions were aimed at improving our own internal workflows while others focused on the services we offer to other staff and students at the University.

See [this blog article](#) for more details of what we did together.

Contact Us

Research Software Group

Information about the Research Software Group: <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/rsg>

For anything related to research software at the University of Birmingham please email bear-rsg@contacts.bham.ac.uk

For anything related to research data science at the University of Birmingham please email rdsci-team@contacts.bham.ac.uk

Advanced Research Computing

Information about ARC and the Birmingham Environment for Academic Research: <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/bear>

For general help and information on BEAR services (BlueBEAR HPC, Research Data Store, ...) please email bearinfo@contacts.bham.ac.uk

Check out the BEAR Blog: <https://blog.bham.ac.uk/bear>

Requests, Faults, Complaints

The IT Service Desk is your route to find answers. Find all ARC items: <https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/bear/sd/bear>

All other IT Services items/help or to log faults: <https://www.itservicedesk.bham.ac.uk/>